

Emotional Universal Design – Beyond Usability of Products

Sooshin Choi, Industrial Design, University of Cincinnati - USA

Abstract

Universal design aims to promote the quality of human life regardless of the physical, cognitive, educational, cultural, financial, gender and age-based differences. It works to improve the usability and accessibility of products and systems. However, universal design products are often misunderstood as being ugly, stigmatizing and costly.

If a product answers aged users' needs and demands, it is assumed to not attract younger users' attention. Similarly, if a product is designed for females, it does not seem to appeal to male users in most cases. Also, a product aimed at blind users does not convince people with normal vision. Apparently, these false conceptions construct a huge obstacle for the successful development of universal design products and methods.

While there are many ways to apply universal design methods to the industrial design cycle of products, an emotional design approach can improve such products' acceptability. It not only enhances the aesthetics of the product, but helps in making the product more intuitive by creating strong motivation to use the product. It is also found that the emotional design can reduce the rate of misuse by creating a stronger connection between the user and the product.

This paper discusses how emotional design can support universal design. An example design process by students is shown to demonstrate how emotional design can improve the universality of a product.

Keywords: Emotion and Universal Design, Universality, Usability.

Introduction

This paper will introduce the importance of universal design in products and the fact that not many everyday-use products have good universality. It argues the reason why universal design is not actively applied in the product development cycle and outlines the obstacles in designing more universal products.

Further, it discusses how the emotional design approach can help people and manufacturers in accepting universally designed products and how it will eventually improve our quality of life in our communities. The paper will introduce methods and a process with examples.

Need of Universal Design

Universal design or inclusive design aims to create design that works for as many people as possible. It is often misinterpreted as creating a design solution that either works for all human beings or only for people who have special needs, but the correct concept is creating designs that can be used by a diverse pool of users without making any special adaptations or modifications to the product.

A set of principles of universal design has been developed by the Center for Universal Design at North Carolina State University, they constitute the most generic and accepted principles so far:

1. **Equitable Use**
The design is useful and marketable to people with diverse abilities.
2. **Flexibility in Use**
The design accommodates a wide range of individual preferences & abilities.
3. **Simple & Intuitive**
Use of the design is easy to understand.
4. **Perceptible Information**
The design communicates info effectively, despite conditions or the sensory abilities.
5. **Tolerance for Error**
The design minimizes hazards & the consequences of accidental actions.

6. Low Physical Effort
The design is efficient & comfortable and requires minimum fatigue.
7. Size and Space for Approach and Use
Appropriate size and space.

These principles focus more on the usability and ergonomic issues, the emotional design aspect tends to remain ignored.

Universal Design and Product Design

There is no argument that calculates how much universal design is beneficial to various people in this global and diverse society. During the past two decades, since the concept of universal design was coined by Ron Mace, our environment has become much more accessible to a wide variety of people who were not able to enjoy an equal life and the living environment much. In other countries and continents, concepts such as inclusive design and shareable product¹ have been contributing in producing an equal opportunity of quality of life for almost everyone.

However, this trend is mainly observed in architecture and interior spaces. According to the ADA (Americans with Disabilities Act), public r should have enough space for wheelchair users to transfer to and from the wheelchair. All the signage should have braille for blind users. There are so many examples of how the ADA Standards for Accessible Design² regulates the design of the public environment. A good example would be the lavatories in public buildings. If a public building is not designed and built properly, it has to be modified to comply with the regulation. The main focuses of the ADA or universal design in environment and architecture is the space and accessibility.

Products are different from buildings in a few ways. Products in most cases;

- have consumers or purchasers,
- are meant to be mass-produced,
- are meant to be possessed,

¹ Sharable products or Kyoyo-Hin are designed to be used by as many people as possible, including the elderly and those with disabilities. <http://kyoyohin.org/eng/index.html>

² US Department of Justice. <http://www.usdoj.gov/crt/ada/adastd94.pdf>

- have a greater number of options,
- have no legislative pressure to be universal for all potential users, and
- may cost more if they are adjustable or customizable.

These differences are the obstacles for development of universal design products. However, the emotional design approach will be one of the ways to overcome this hindrance.

Emotional Design and Universal Design

Many universal design approaches fail in improving usability and appealing to a broad range of users. Designers tend to focus on the physical and cognitive aspects of controls and displays to make the usability better, but often the design result in too mechanic and less human.

Designers often aim at the elderly and people with special needs by making the design physically easy to use, and the result is a product that is less appealing the rest of the users.

These problems can be resolved by the emotional design approach. The emotional aspect of design will have several benefits making products more universal.

1. Emotional design increases usability by creating mental attachment with users.
2. Emotional design decreases or eliminates social stigma.
3. When functionality is taken for granted, emotional appeal becomes the brand differentiator.

Most users are emotionally attached to the products that have pretty, friendly, familiar, soft, warm appearance and touch. While all products have to be functionally perfect, research shows users demonstrate higher response to the products they feel emotionally attached to, and this increases the use and decreases the chance of misuse, thus enhancing the usability of products.

Examples of Emotional Universal Design Products

Public products – Water Fountain

Most water fountains are designed from a functional standpoint, i.e. how to open (and close) the valve, supply and drainage of water, cost, and maintenance. There are emotionally designed fountains, but they are often less comfortable to use.

Figure 1: Various water fountains

Fountains are mostly designed for people with no special needs or challenges; and this leaves children, wheelchair users, and people with limited motor skills to experience difficulty in reaching and drinking water from the fountain. To resolve this, sometimes there are low-mounted fountains installed next to normal ones. However, the solution is still solely based on physical and anthropometric needs of the users, and there is no emotional aspect involved in the design. People who “have to” drink from the low-mounted water fountain often feels that they need special care and can often be left feeling segregated. Since water fountains are for all people, they should be designed to use with pleasure regardless of different needs the user might have.

Figure 2: Water fountain in Sydney

A water fountain installed in Centre Quay in Sydney, Australia is a good example of how emotional design approach can make a product universal. The fountain is located on the wide sidewalk and the design of it matches very nicely with palm trees around the area. The fountain itself is curved and cantilevered so that wheelchair users/ children can get closer to the spout.

Moreover, for users without any disabilities, instead of moving their heads above the water basin in normal fountains, actually “hug” the fountain. This creates emotional contact or emotional interplay while drinking water. When you “hug”, your hand goes naturally to the button making it very intuitive. The curved “leaf” lets excess water flow to the drain at its base, so there isn’t any stagnant water that often gets contaminated in normal fountains. This design not only creates a healthy environment, but also invites users to come closer.

In reflection to the universal design principles, it meets all the requirements. Furthermore, it creates an emotional connection to users. People not only use it, but they tend to enjoy drinking water from it. This is good evidence of how an emotional design approach can make products more universal.

Medical Product –

Most of the medical devices look and work without any emotional interaction with patients as well as operators. This often leads to unfamiliar procedures becoming even more awkward. Philips’ Kitten Scanner is a good example of how a medical device could be emotionally accessed by people who are not familiar with and are even scared of medical devices.

Designed specifically for children scheduled for a CT scan, the Kitten Scanner lets them 'scan' a stuffed elephant or their own toys at the touch of a button. Animation appears on a screen that shows children what doctors are looking for inside the toy and tells them a story about each one. The aim is to show them how the machine works and to help ease any anxiety they may be feeling. While the product is not the actual product the patient will be scanned with, its emotional value makes the patient less scared and they even enjoy being scanned.

Figure 3: Kitten Scanner. Photo courtesy of Philips

Another popular example of a medical device or assistive product is the hearing aid. Since the hearing aid is mainly used among elderly people and people with impaired hearing, showing the hearing aid is not what the user is proud of. Many attempts were made to make the design of the hearing aid less stigmatizing by reducing its size, however doing so usually reduces the sound quality. The hearing aids always end up being a device which the users don't want to show others around them. The design of Hearing System LEONARDO by Hansaton is a good example of an invisible yet high quality device. The appearance of Leonardo is similar to the latest Bluetooth receiver, so no one would figure the user has a hearing difficulty. It has an unobtrusive appearance, as it easily sits inside the ears. Furthermore, it comes in 11 different colors and the users have an option of customizing them to meet their needs. The fit of the device is very secure – the curved shape of the device fits around the ear to let the wearer maintain everyday life with no worry of losing the hearing aid, yet another benefit of universal design.

Figure 4: Hearing System LEONARDO. Photo courtesy of Hansaton Hearing Systems

Consumer Product –

Universal design helps equalize the life of people with various challenges with the lives of people who have fewer or no challenges. As most products are designed for people who can operate the product easily, many people who have any level of challenge will suffer and be excluded from using the product. Most assistive products are functional but not emotionally designed and they may even have social stigma.

Oxo, a kitchen tool manufacturer, is a forerunner of applying universal design to everyday products. Starting from the Good Grips potato peeler, Oxo has made various tools for people with and without physical challenges. Smooth Edge Can Opener cuts on the side of the can below the can edge, leaving no sharp edges on the can or lid. The easy-to-turn, side-wind knob requires less force and features Oxo's non-slip, comfortable grip. Enjoy a safer, hygienic, and easy way to open small and large cans. The Smooth Edge Can Opener is an emotional design that promotes principles 1. **EQUITABLE USE**, 3. **SIMPLE & INTUITIVE USE**, and 6. **LOW PHYSICAL EFFORT**. It is not only usable for people with special needs, but is also appealing to most people.

Figure 5: Oxo Smooth Edge Can Opener. Photo courtesy of OXO International Ltd.

Universal Design Process

A typical universal design approach is very similar to any product design cycle.

A common product design process can be described as follows.

1. Research users and resources to understand problems
 - Define target user profiles and scenarios.
 - Collect demand from market and manufacturer.
 - Create design criteria
2. Ideations to discover possible solutions
 - Make sketches and mock-ups to initiate design ideas.
3. Synthesize ideas to create useful solutions
 - Make renderings and models to combine potential ideas.
4. Test the solutions to validate
 - Perform usability tests to validate the design

The main difference of the universal design process is in phase 1 - understanding the users and making plausible scenarios. In most design projects, designers (and clients) create “target users” to focus on narrowly defined users to maximize the effect. The target market is usually the largest market segment where there is a big chunk of customers with lots of disposable money. This “target market strategy” is developed in the business marketing field.

The advantage of focusing on the target market for the designer is making it easy to understand the users’ characteristics and demand. The reason why most corporations target the major user group is because it is easy to see where the money is. The benefit of target market strategy for the users in the market segment is getting the product designed to meet their needs. However, this leaves people who are not in the target market segment excluded from use of the products or to experience difficulty using them.

The main difference of the process for universal design products is defining the “target” users. In the research phase, designers or the manufacturer need to define the market as wide as possible. This way, people who used to be excluded from the use of the product can be

included. This way, manufacturers can expand the market or find a new market opportunity. This way, the designer can find new design momentum. The ideal universal design process would be as follows.

1. Research users and resources to understand problems
 - Create potential market segment expansion to include users with various needs.
 - Collect physical and cognitive needs of inclusive user group.
 - Define inclusive user profiles and scenarios.
 - Measure universal design performance of referential products.
2. Ideations to discover possible solutions
 - Making sketches and mock-ups to initiate design ideas.
3. Synthesize ideas to create useful solutions
 - Make renderings and models to combine potential ideas.
4. Test the solutions to validate
 - User trials with potential users with different needs and characteristics.

Universal design process with emotional design emphasis will focus on the emotional quality that users want in the phase 1 and develop forms and user interfaces that carry the emotional quality. The designer should take notice of how the emotional design increases the usability and decreases the stigma.

The emotional universal design process will look like this.

1. Research users and resources to understand problems
 - Create potential market segment expansion to include various types of users.
 - Collect physical, cognitive, and emotional needs of inclusive user group.
 - Define inclusive user profiles and scenarios.
 - Measure universal design performances of referential products.
2. Ideations to discover possible solutions
 - Create forms and design ideas that reflect the emotional qualities.
3. Synthesize ideas to create useful solutions

- Make renderings and models to combine potential ideas.
4. Test the solutions to validate
- User trials with potential users with different needs and characteristics.
 - Test the usability of the design

Figure 6: Universal Design Process

The major difference is discovering emotional needs besides the physical and cognitive needs. Most medical products, for example wheel chairs or walkers, meet physical and cognitive needs but have no emotional value in their designs, and thus no one would like to use the product. Enhancing the emotional value should be one of the important parts of design which are more universal.

Since aesthetic design is one of the traditional features of industrial design, designers can create a number of potential emotional design solutions without sacrificing physical and cognitive usability. In fact, an emotional design solution will enhance the usability of the product.

Example process

The process of universal design with emotional design emphasis was tested in an industrial design studio at the University of Cincinnati in winter quarter, 2006 with 18 students. Third-

year students designed blood pressure monitors that have to be usable and appealing to users with diverse needs. The assignment was aimed at redesigning the blood pressure monitor that is used by professionals and by individuals in their daily lives.

First, students re-defined the target market and the users to find the opportunities to include people with special needs. This is a very important step not only for the users but the manufacturers as companies can find opportunity to expand the market segment. It solves the most fundamental obstacle for universal design being success.

Personas

Jason
29 years old
Male
6'5", large
sales rep
has a working wife and a home
lives in a city-suburb
spends nearly half the month on the road
high stress life and high blood pressure
checks once in the evening
also has type II diabetes
drinks a lot of caffeine during the day
very unorganized

33 years of age
Female
Single
lives in a large city
has a 9 to 5 desk job
works out every morning before work
belongs to a gym and uses the aerobic machines
takes public transportation to work
is really into nutrition
checks occasionally
likes to check at work
is concerned about the health effects of her job
strong near-sighted
fashion conscious

Emily
77 years of age
Female
Mexican American
home maker
cooks a lot of the meals
lives with her daughter and 3 children
works most of the day in her kitchen
likes to run errands from 1 thru 3pm
checks twice a day at 10am and 7pm
has high blood pressure
is at risk for strokes and many illnesses
has a bad left hand from a stroke
likes to check her families pressure

Sara

trouble zones

Figure 7: Three personas for blood pressure monitor. Michael Shadovitz

Each student selected an expanded market and created three representative user profiles or *personas*. In this step the designer will find what kind of characteristics they have and what sort of design solutions they need. Designers should create very distinct personas to avoid overlaps and to include a wider range of population from the target sample to increase coverage of all potential users.

This is a very important step for the manufacturer too as it will help in finding potential market expansion. In fact, this is the most essential part for the promotion of application of universal design to product development.

Figure 8: A persona map. Michael Shadovitz

Through this creation of personas and a persona map, students get the idea about the values that the users need. Since the focus is on developing universal design with an emotional approach and solutions, students envision all possible - visceral, behavioral, and reflective emotional – solutions.³

The students then test current products to find product opportunity gaps. It is best if they have access to those actual personas. In studio, it was found that current products do not have functional problems. However, many products either had the appearance of a 'medical' product or they were not easy to use if the user had a certain physical challenge be it visual, auditory or motor.

³ Norman, Donald. Emotional Design: Why We Love (Or Hate) Everyday Things,

Figure 9: Students are testing existing blood pressure monitors

The next step involved was customizing the Universal Design Performance Measure for Products. The UD Performance Measure was developed based on the principles of universal design at the Center for Universal Design, North Carolina State University. It is used widely to validate universality of generic products. The original UD Performance Measure is an evaluation tool as well as design criteria for universal design. If a product meets more items than other products, the product is “measured” to be more universal. The measure has 29 items that branch out from seven UD principles; they are of physical or cognitive issues except one item that reads “1D – The product appeals to all potential users”. The item 1D talks about emotional universality in a broad sense, which is adequate for making the product not only useful but free from stigma. It also talks about the marketing potential, which affects most manufacturers’ decision making. The UD Performance Measure helps reveal both design opportunity for designers and market opportunity for the manufacturers. When current designs are evaluated designers can find items whose designs got low ratings those items are the areas to improve.

Students were asked to modify the UD Performance Measure in order to make it more specific for the product and the usage of the users described in the persona. Bertholt Schroeder removed the item 6D – “The product can be used without having to rest afterward” because it does not apply to the particular product category. He inserted a new item “The product is enjoyable to use” to measure the level of satisfactory in usage. Another student included a new item “The product looks like an everyday product” to attest the level of stigma of the product.

Universal Design Performance Measures for Products

VERSION 1.0

PRINCIPLE ONE EQUITABLE USE	No Physical Effort	Simple/Right Design	Minimal	Large	Simple/Right	Comments
1A. All potential users could use this product in essentially the same way, regardless of differences in their abilities.						
1B. Potential users could use this product without feeling embarrassed or stigmatized because of differences in personal capabilities.						
1C. Potential users of this product have access to all features of privacy, security, and safety, regardless of personal capabilities.						
1D. This product appeals to all potential users.						
PRINCIPLE TWO FLEXIBILITY IN USE						
2A. Every potential user can find at least one way to use this product effectively.						
2B. This product can be used with either the right or left hand alone.						
2C. This product facilitates (or does not require) user accuracy and precision.						
2D. This product can be used at whatever pace (quickly or slowly) the user prefers.						
PRINCIPLE THREE SIMPLE AND INTUITIVE USE						
3A. This product is as simple and straightforward as it can be.						
3B. An untrained person could use this product without instructions.						
3C. Any potential user can understand the language used in this product.						
3D. The most important features of this product are the most obvious.						
3E. This product provides feedback to the user.						
PRINCIPLE FOUR PERCEPTIBLE INFORMATION						
4A. This product can be used without hearing.						
4B. This product can be used without sight.						
4C. The features of this product can be clearly described in words (e.g., in instruction manuals or on telephone help lines).						
4D. This product can be used by persons who use assistive devices (e.g., eyeglasses, hearing aids, sign language, or service animals).						
PRINCIPLE FIVE TOLERANCE FOR ERROR						
5A. Product features are arranged according to their importance.						
5B. This product draws the user's attention to errors or hazards.						
5C. If the user makes a mistake with this product, it won't cause damage or injure the user.						
5D. This product prompts the user to pay attention during critical tasks.						
PRINCIPLE SIX LOW PHYSICAL EFFORT						
6A. This product can be used comfortably (e.g., without awkward movements or postures).						
6B. This product can be used by someone who is weak or tired.						
6C. This product can be used without repeating any motion enough to cause fatigue or pain.						
6D. This product can be used without having to rest afterward.						
PRINCIPLE SEVEN SIZE AND SPACE FOR APPROACH AND USE						
7A. It is easy for a person of any size to see all the important elements of this product from any position (e.g., standing or seated).						
7B. It is easy for a person of any size to reach all the important elements of this product from any position (e.g., standing or seated).						
7C. This product can be used by a person with hands of any size.						
7D. There is enough space to use this product with devices or assistance (e.g., wheelchair, oxygen tank, or service animal).						

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UNIVERSAL DESIGN PERFORMANCE MEASURES FOR PRODUCTS

PRINCIPLE ONE - EQUITABLE USE	No Physical Effort	Simple/Right Design	Minimal	Large	Simple/Right	Comments
All potential users could use this product in essentially the same way, regardless of differences in mobility.						Wrist reader is more difficult to put on. Someone with really low mobility would have difficulty.
All potential users could use this product in essentially the same way, regardless of differences in ability.						Wristc and right-impaired people would not be able to use this product.
This product appeals to all potential users.						Aesthetics are not flashy to they would attract a larger spectrum.
PRINCIPLE TWO - FLEXIBILITY IN USE						
The product can be used with either the right or the left hand.						There is no difficulty in using this product with either hand.
This product does not require user precision and accuracy.						By nature of the product it needs to be put on in a specific place.
This product can be used at whatever pace (quickly or slowly) that the user prefers.						Product can be put on a started whenever the user is ready.
Every user can find at least one way to use this product effectively.						An amless person would not be able to use this product.
PRINCIPLE THREE - SIMPLE AND INTUITIVE USE						
This product is as simple and straightforward as it can be.						Bloop reader has good self explanatory graphics. Item buttons could be clearer as to their function. Wrist reader does not have good image directions.
An untrained person can use this product without instructions.						Wrist could probably intuitively figure out how to use it but there is a level of ambiguity because a specific action needs to be carried out to use the product properly.
The most important features of this product are the most obvious.						The buttons stand out especially on the bloop reader.
This product provides feedback to the user.						Both products give feedback through the readout screen.
PRINCIPLE FOUR - PERCEPTIBLE INFORMATION						
This product can be used without hearing.						A person with hearing disabilities would not have any problems using these products.
This product can be used without sight.						People without sight would not be able to use this alone.
This product can be used without literacy.						Wristc people would not be able to use this product.
The features of this product can easily be described in words.						The features can easily be described verbally.
PRINCIPLE FIVE - TOLERANCE FOR ERROR						
Product features are arranged according to their importance.						Arrangement could be better but most important functions are fairly obvious.
This product draws user's attention to errors or hazards (namely incorrectly putting on the device).						Display readout warns of error but has no indication of whether the user has correctly put on the bands.
If user makes a mistake with this product, it won't cause damage or injure the user.						Product is safe.
PRINCIPLE SIX - LOW PHYSICAL EFFORT						
This product can be used without awkward movements or postures.						Some movements are awkward but necessary.
This product can be used by someone who is weak or tired.						Use of product is not physically intensive.
This product does not physically over-exert the user.						Product does not take much energy to use.
PRINCIPLE SEVEN - SIZE AND SPACE FOR APPROACH AND USE						
A person can see the important elements of this product whether they are standing or sitting.						Readout on wrist is pretty clear. Readout for bloop is pretty clear visible.
All the important elements of this product can be reached from a standing or sitting position.						Bloop readout is harder to reach if standing.
This product can be used by a person with hands of any size.						Hand size is no problem.
There is enough space to use this product to be used without it getting in the way of other devices (wheelchair, O2 tank, etc.).						Product does not take up much room.

▲ Wrist blood pressure reader
 ■ Bloop blood pressure reader
 ● New blood pressure reader

Figure 10: UD performance measure for product – original (left) and modified version

After finding design opportunities from the assessment of current products, students developed concept design sketches and models to test how people would use the products <figure 10.>. At this stage, models are made of quick and easy materials to validate designs without investing too much time.

Figure 11: Concept designs of blood pressure monitor

Design A (top left - Designer: Paige Fissel) is inspired by personal jewelries and is designed for people who need to carry the monitor all the time but do not want to show it as a medical necessity. The monitor and its peripherals resemble a pendant and ring. They do not appear as medical devices, thus the design is free from stigmatism.

Design B (top right - Designer: Jason Rupert) is a finger-type blood pressure monitor in a handle shape. It does not look anything like a medical device due to its warm-curved design language. Rather it looks like a hand exerciser or a toy. It is highly usable for those with arthritis or a weak grip as it does not use Velcro bands that are common in blood pressure monitors.

Design C (bottom left - Designer: Matt Grote) is a monitor with popular electronic gadget appearance, such as an MP3 Player. While the large window and buttons make it easy to use, its gently curved surface makes it friendlier to touch and use.

Design D (bottom right - Designer: Noel Gauthier) uses design elements from personal sports gadgets. The brand (Nike) used in this design makes it look like a non-medical device, ridding it of stigmatic bias.

These design solutions/ prototypes were totally different that the earlier 'medical' look and feel of current blood pressure monitors. They were aesthetically more pleasing, more usable and addressed the need of a wider population with various disabilities.

Conclusion and Future Assignment

Emotional design promotes universal design. It increases usability and decreases stigma. It increases sales and decreases negative bias against the product. The universal design process with emphasis on an emotional aspect showed that design will be more useful and appealing. Designers enjoyed the wider range of possibility of possibility in making universal design. It benefits all.

The process of universal design needs various users' participation in problem definition as well as at the design validation stage. This is a common constraint in the college level studio as it is hard to recruit these real users as and when they are needed. Because of time and resource constraints we were unable to obtain feedback from the real users. We believe that we will be able to report the findings of the user testing in the next paper.

References

American Society of Interior Designers (1993), *Universal Design Programs: A Two-Part Program Package for the Design Professions*, ASID Education Department and ASID Government and Public Affairs Department: Washington, DC

Christophersen, Jon (2002), *Universal Design: 17 Ways of Thinking and Teaching*, Husbanken: Oslo

Choi, Sooshin (2005), *Universal Design: A Practical Tool for Diverse Society*, The International Conference of Diversity on Communities, Organizations, and Nations, Melbourne, Australia

Choi, Sooshin (2005), *Strategic Use of Universal Design as a Business Tool for 21st Century*, MX Design Conference, Iberoamericana University, Mexico City

Clarkson, John [et al.] (eds) (2003), *Inclusive Design: Design for the Whole Population*, Springer: London; New York

Covington, George A., Hannah, Bruce (1997), *Access by Design*, Van Nostrand Reinhold, New York

Keates, Simeon [et al.] (2004), *Designing a More Inclusive World*, Springer: London; NY

Leibrock, Cynthia A. and Terry, James Evan (1999), *Beautiful Universal Design*, John Wiley: New York

Mace, Ronald L., Hardie, Graeme J., and Place, Jaine P. (1990), *Accessible Environments: Toward Universal Design*, Center for Accessible Housing, North Carolina State University: Raleigh, NC

Norman, Donald (2005), *Emotional Design: Why We Love (Or Hate) Everyday Things*, Basic Books: NY

Preiser, Wolfgang F.E. (2001), editor in chief, *Universal Design Handbook*, McGraw-Hill: New York

US Department of Justice, *ADA Standards for Accessible Design*,
<http://www.usdoj.gov/crt/ada/adastd94.pdf>